
Research

Assessing the Quality of Aviation Ground Logistics Services: A Case Study of Buyantukha Airport in Mongolia

Badraljargal Bayarchuluun^{1*}, Jiang Yan¹

¹ School of Economics and Management, Dalian Jiaotong University, Dalian, Liaoning, 116028, China

Abstract: With the rapid development of the global economy and the acceleration of globalization, Mongolia's air logistics industry has brought considerable economic benefits to the economic market. However, at present, Mongolia's air logistics industry is still in a vigorous development stage, and the logistics service quality assessment lacks mature theoretical system support. Although the market is lucrative, how to regulate and improve the quality of logistics services has encountered many difficulties. By analyzing the actual situation of Mongolia's international aviation airport, this paper discusses its advantages and shortcomings in air logistics services, and provides reference experience and practices for the development of service quality in Mongolia.

Keywords: Aviation ground logistics; Service quality evaluation; Mongolia International Airport

*Corresponding Author

Accepted: 08 April, 2023; **Published:** 16 April, 2023

How to cite this article: Badraljargal Bayarchuluun, Jiang Yan, (2023). Assessing the Quality of Aviation Ground Logistics Services: A Case Study of Buyantukha Airport in Mongolia. *North American Academic Research*, 6(4), 132-138. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7834374>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2023 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

I. Introduction

With the increasing expansion of air cargo business at home and abroad, the market competitive position is increasing, air transport services are increasingly valued, and the competition between airports is intensifying. Only by continuously improving its competitiveness and actively expanding its competitiveness and service level can the airport survive in the fierce market competition. Therefore, the quality of service is of great significance for the development of airports [1]. Service quality is an important factor that determines the competitiveness of airports, and airports can only better improve customer satisfaction by continuously improving service quality during development. However, at present, the domestic air logistics service industry is still facing the challenges of intensified competition for domestic airports and relatively different from overseas air cargo business needs. In this case, taking Mongolia's airport as an example, analyzing the current situation of service quality is helpful to better understand the status of international airport service quality, so as to provide useful reference for improving the service quality of domestic airports.

Xia Huiyong and Zhu Zhiyu emphasized that the airport service work evaluation system can reduce the workload and improve the efficiency of the work[2]. Hu Bing used SWOT analysis to analyze the development of China's air logistics

industry and gave corresponding countermeasures [3]. Based on the difference between airport passengers' expectations and actual perception of airport passenger service quality, Liu Yumin et al. established an improved service quality model, and verified the effectiveness of the model through empirical analysis. Efficient airport logistics service quality has been proven to increase customer satisfaction[4]. Wang Yiru et al. have built a more comprehensive airport cargo terminal logistics service quality evaluation system from the three levels of physics, affairs and human management, which can effectively improve the service capacity of airport cargo terminal [5]. Tian Xue et al. built a customer-centric evaluation system for airport logistics service quality indicators, and proposed that airport logistics business outsourcing, infrastructure and service informatization level are the key to improving logistics services[6]. Through the above literature analysis, it can be seen that there are relatively few studies on airport service quality, and many studies are not specific to airports. Therefore, this study takes Buyantuha International Airport in Mongolia as an example, analyzes the current situation of service work and the problems existing in the service work of Mongolia, and puts forward reasonable suggestions, so as to accelerate the development of Mongolian airport service and enhance the competitiveness of Mongolian airport.

2. The characteristics of aviation ground logistics services

Air transport refers to the use of the airport as the main medium, with the help of the global flight network provided by the airport and the resource advantages of air transportation, and at the same time the use of modern network technology, efficient integration of various means of transportation and other means of transportation, efficient connection of the supply side and demand side, to achieve the efficient transmission of materials from the origin to the end point.

Air express companies can integrate processing services, logistics services, handling services, packaging services, information consulting services and information exchange, forming a relatively complete business chain and providing more complete services for enterprise customers. Air logistics takes air transportation as the main means, specifically involving commodity warehousing, ground distribution, transportation, logistics agency and other service functions.

(1) A perfect air transport enterprise service system is composed of three parts: airport enterprises + aviation and other transport companies. For a region, the airport business is a monopoly, with only a few to dozens of companies, and hundreds of others (from first-party logistics to fourth-party logistics). In summary, ground transportation is the four transportation components of coordination, storage, logistics and distribution with airport operations as the core.

(2) Aviation ground logistics distribution has great user participation. Customer engagement service is the main feature of ground logistics distribution. Air logistics is different from ordinary commercial supply chains. Because the customers of the ordinary supply chain are usually at the end of the aircraft commercial chain and are the ultimate customer goals of the enterprise, but the customers of the air cargo business chain are at both ends of the aircraft ground transportation chain, which objectively requires synchronous information communication and multi-point two-way contact between the ground transportation enterprise and the aircraft second-end customer, so as to achieve the rapid response of the enterprise to customer requirements.

(iii) Highly systematic air and land logistics. Packaging, storage, loading and unloading, distribution, etc. are the basic components of modern logistics, and at the same time are the specific executors of modern logistics systems, forming the fundamental requirements of modern logistics industry. From air freight forwarding companies to ground logistics companies, they need to cooperate closely to complete the above tasks in order to serve users more efficiently.

(4) Aviation ground logistics services have complete customer demand responsiveness. From the perspective of the type of the entire logistics service chain, ground logistics service is a typical demand-based supply chain. The non-storable and non-transferable nature of air logistics determines that there can be no "inventory" that can be produced and stored in advance, so aviation ground logistics services must be demand-driven. If there is no customer demand, there will be no object for each link of service, and a series of operations cannot occur in the entire service chain.

3. The current situation of ground logistics services at Mongolian airports

3.1 Overview of Buyantukha International Airport in Mongolia

This paper selects BUYANT UKHAA International Airport, the largest airport in Western Mongolia and the only international airport in Ulaanbaatar. The airport has opened international and domestic routes, and there are regular flights to China, Russia, South Korea, Germany and Japan. In 2022, about 640,000 passengers were transported by air. However, because the aircraft can only take off and land in one direction, it is greatly affected by the climate, so the delay rate of the aircraft is also higher.

3.2 Problems with ground logistics services at Buyantuha Airport

At present, Mongolia's air cargo is still in the state of "shipper delivery, consignee pick-up", and has not really achieved "whole-process logistics", and "multimodal transport" is rare. This model aims to maximize freight capacity and meet the production needs of air freight companies, hindering its organic integration with air freight business, thereby limiting its development. Specifically, it is:

(1) The civil aviation logistics support system is not perfect. In general, the current air logistics industry in Mongolia has problems such as small scale and low cargo transportation capacity. Its business field is narrow, mainly only one air cargo or one air cargo intermediary, its logistics management and technology are relatively backward, its service quality needs to be further improved. The supply is mainly general goods, and high-end goods such as high surcharges and express delivery account for a low proportion, which does not fully reflect the advantages of the aviation industry. Not compatible with rapidly evolving needs.

(2) There are problems in the logistics distribution system. Under the modern economic conditions characterized by informatization and networking, the competition between air transport enterprises is becoming more and more fierce. The same aircraft, the same distance, naturally it is impossible to see the advantages and disadvantages of the opponent. With the continuous expansion of the commercial chain, it has brought more development space for the aviation industry. To achieve this, a fast and efficient land-based distribution network will be a powerful tool for competitors.

(3) Lack of a perfect logistics resource sharing platform. First, information in the public transport system cannot be shared. All kinds of transportation vehicles develop independently and lack interconnection, and the traffic data in the public transport system is in multiple departments and regions, which cannot achieve the interconnection and sharing of data. It is difficult to provide effective information support for the optimal allocation of transportation resources. Because it does not have comprehensive logistics informatization capabilities, the cargo transportation mode it is engaged in is relatively single, so it is difficult to meet the requirements of modern logistics. Second, there is a lack of a consistent technical specification. The technical specifications of different modes of transportation are inconsistent, and there is a lack of effective docking and cooperation, resulting in low operational efficiency, which affects the operational efficiency and service quality of the entire transportation system.

(4) Mongolian enterprises are facing greater pressure on the growth of production costs. Soaring oil prices and rising labor costs have all contributed to higher logistics costs. Due to the rising international oil prices, the price of oil in Mongolia is also at a high level. Some companies even say they can't hold on. Some were even forced to change jobs. As prices continue to rise, people's living expenses are also increasing sharply, which causes people's wages to rise day by day, which causes the continuous growth of labor costs, and logistics companies are also affected by the continuous increase in labor costs.

(5) Excessive security inspections reduce the efficiency of receiving goods. When entering the warehouse through the security inspection, for various reasons, multiple security inspections will be carried out on the items, which will adversely affect the speed of the security inspection and the transmission speed of the items, and will also reduce the efficiency of the work and operation of the staff.

(6) Multiple blocks are repeatedly assembled, resulting in unnecessary labor hours and labor consumption. After the goods are loaded onto the container, the outbound department must reassemble the previously unassigned goods to a specific container, resulting in repeated operations and a great impact on the transportation efficiency of the goods.

(7) Rough behavior that may occur during the handling process. When the operator carries out the assembly operation, due to the large amount of operation, tight operation time, and large amount of operation, it is easy to throw, trample and other situations, that is, rough handling problems.

(8) The content of information technology is not high, and the working methods are outdated. In the process of cargo entering the port, there is only one civilian staff on the cargo information on each aircraft, and the verification and entry of cargo information need to be carried out manually one by one, which will not only affect the work efficiency of the staff, but also errors will occur in the process of information entry.

4. Evaluation of the quality of ground logistics services at Mongolian airports

The improvement of service level is related to the survival and development of the air logistics industry, and enterprises to improve service level, need to start from the most critical factor affecting service level - enterprise productivity level, try to improve the lag problem of air transport industry productivity, and improve logistics service level by improving their own productivity level. Productivity is composed of many aspects, so as an airline, we must also take all possible effective ways to improve productivity and base product quality on objective science.

4.1 Causes of aviation ground logistics service quality evaluation

Logistics service is a very complex process, so customers' evaluation of the service quality of logistics enterprises is subject to a variety of factors

The influence of such factors. The company's external image, customer expectations and technical quality are three very key and general aspects.

Before customers receive logistics services, because of the influence of the external image of the logistics company and other customers' evaluation of the logistics company, they have a basic understanding of the company in their minds, that is, the customer has a degree of expectation for the company's service, and the customer accepts the company's service with the expectation of the company, in this process, the customer will unconsciously compare the service quality they feel with the quality expected by the company, and then make a very satisfactory service quality of the company. Satisfied or unsatisfactory ratings.

Since customers are very concerned about the results achieved by logistics services, technical quality plays a decisive role in the service quality evaluation of logistics companies. However, with the fierce competition in the logistics industry, customers will pay more and more attention to the quality of logistics technology, if customers in the receipt of logistics services, produced some dissatisfied experience, then, even if the final logistics service, that is, technical quality is the same, the overall rating of customers for logistics service quality will be very different. Therefore, when establishing the logistics service quality evaluation index, it is necessary to pay attention not only to technical quality, but also to functional quality.

According to the above reasons, the comprehensive opinions of Mongolian aviation managers, passengers and scholars, and the reference to a large number of existing research literature, on the basis of the construction of airport logistics service quality evaluation index system, the specific situation of which is shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Evaluation scale of ground logistics service quality at airports in Mongolia

Level 1 indicators	Level 2 indicators
Flight ticketing service	Telephone consultation services Ticket delivery service Ticket collection service Notification of ticket and boarding information Notification of flight changes
Ground service	velocity Collect and run the Baggage service Seat selection Waiting guidance service Flight information communication services Self-service check-in convenience
Quality of flight operations	Flight security Flight punctuality Ease of flight
Air Services	Cabin service Cabin environment Crew grooming Flight attendant service initiative Security demonstrations and inspections Broadcast services Books, newspapers and magazines Quality of audiovisual services Variety and quality of catering Bathroom cleaning Seat pitch and comfort
Arrival station service	Speed of baggage pickup Baggage tracking service Baggage compensation service Transit services

4.2 Optimization method of aviation ground logistics service problems

Aviation ground logistics distribution information system, from the business point of view, is composed of aviation ground logistics distribution information service network subsystem, aviation ground logistics distribution information service subsystem, aviation ground logistics distribution information and service management subsystem, aviation ground logistics distribution service information system subsystem, etc. The logistics distribution network subsystem of aviation is usually composed of nodes (supply points, distribution centers, customer demand points) and links (transportation routes between suppliers and distribution centers, distribution routes between distribution centers and customers, and direct routes between suppliers and customers).

The main objectives of air logistics and distribution system optimization can be roughly summarized as "three highs and two lows", that is, high logistics and distribution efficiency, high service standards, high logistics efficiency, low logistics costs, and low pollution, including:

- (1) High distribution efficiency

Achieving larger and higher yields with minimal investment is the goal pursued by individual companies. Only by improving the quality of logistics and distribution can the efficiency of the logistics distribution system be improved.

(2) High customer service level

The cargo owner uses aircraft or ground transportation, mainly out of the pursuit of the timeliness of cargo transportation, especially for some fresh goods, within the agreed time limit to transport the goods to the user intact, so it provides various service tools, that is, quality and quantity of transportation to the user, technical services, technical consultation, support and services for the user, etc., so all aspects of logistics operations must be achieved.

(3) High delivery quality

Air transport commodities mainly refer to goods with greater added value, especially for flammable and explosive dangerous goods, when designing packaging, it is necessary to clearly know the physical, chemical or other specific physical properties of the packaging, and fully consider the external influences and dangers of the packaging in the transportation process, especially during transportation or storage.

5. Strategies for improving the quality of ground logistics services at Mongolian airports

5.1 Improve the comprehensive quality of airport staff

First of all, we must standardize talent recruitment, and we must introduce talents through multiple channels and strictly standardize them, and fundamentally control the quality of employees. Second, we must do a good job in talent training. First, it is necessary to do a good job in compiling courses and compile courses with a strong practical nature based on the practical operation experience of workers. The second is to do a good job in learning implementation, linked to employee performance appraisal, to guide them to take the initiative to learn. The third is to set up a mechanism for serving employees, which can not only give material rewards, but also give spiritual incentives, and become the main indicators of the evaluation of excellent work, so as to stimulate their positive work attitude.

5.2 Implement refined management of ground logistics business outsourcing

The biggest problem faced by the logistics services of airlines at Mongolia International Airport is the low operational efficiency, so there is a low bad rating in the evaluation results of the comprehensive evaluation of "response speed", of which "customs declaration efficiency" is an important attribute of expectation, but its score is also relatively low.

Therefore, it is necessary to establish service values with user interests as the core, and improve service capabilities by carrying out refined operation of ground logistics service outsourcing, such as outsourcing ground express services to multiple express companies at airports, and carrying out "one-stop" service traceability business by taking parallel process measures, while establishing a corresponding traffic guidance system; So as to form a good return on investment incentive mechanism, as far as possible to improve the quality of airport ground express operation.

5.3 Improve airport ground logistics service infrastructure

With the development of the specialization of aircraft cargo terminals, its demand for ground cargo operation facilities is also increasing, including automatic three-dimensional shelves, computer monitoring equipment, all kinds of necessary special vehicles, storage facilities, freight conveyor belts, etc., but due to the different business scope of aircraft cargo terminals, its existing and adopted facilities capacity is also uneven, and some facilities have long been overloaded and cannot achieve normal operation; Some facilities are now vacant and do not work as they should.

It is necessary to establish clear logistics service specifications, and methods such as expanding storage capacity, adopting efficient security inspection devices, increasing temporary storage points for receiving goods, updating and improving logistics facilities, and correctly arranging vehicle routes should be adopted to effectively reduce the burden of logistics operations and improve the quality of personnel operations and procedural operations.

5.4 Establish and improve the supervision mechanism of airlines

Establishing a sound mechanism is the main measure to improve the level of ground transportation services in Mongolia. Effective regulation is to make the service requirements public, so that the public understands what kind of services Mongolian International Airlines should provide. Second, Mongolian International Airlines must appoint a commissioner to supervise, specifically deal with the opinions of tourists, and explore measures to improve the service.

5.5 Strengthen cooperation with other third-party logistics

Through the integration relationship of logistics and information flow formed with Mongolia's local service market, logistics services are more malleable and timely. Data sharing is the core of enterprise value chain management, international airlines should cooperate with logistics agencies and corresponding companies in the industry to jointly establish a data foundation, and jointly conduct research on international airports and air logistics systems, and jointly establish a third-party logistics system, so as to maximize the use of logistics information such as personnel, material resources, financial resources and time, reduce enterprise operation investment, so as to achieve interconnection management within the group, improve the service level of enterprises, and ultimately achieve the purpose of obtaining the highest profits of enterprises.

Aviation ground logistics is recognized by modern society as fast, efficient, flexible, safe a mode of transportation, from the overall cost point of view, aviation ground logistics in the supply chain transportation also has a lot of advantages, it can be said that it has become an important force to promote the world logistics market good and rapid development and the steady improvement of the global economy. However, from the case study of Mongolia International Airport, it can be seen that the current aviation ground logistics service quality still needs to be improved in many aspects, and after establishing a complete evaluation system, corresponding measures should be taken to improve the quality. Only in this way can we truly become a brand airport trusted by customers.

6. References

- [1] Park J W, Seyeon J. Transfer Passengers' Perceptions of Airport Service Quality: A Case Study of Incheon International Airport[J]. *International Business Research*, 2011, 4(3).
- [2] 夏慧永, 朱志愚, 王宗宝, 马景禄. 机场旅客服务质量评价系统研究[J]. *江苏科技信息*, 2015(10):16-18.
- [3] 胡冰. 基于产业竞争力视角分析我国航空物流产业运行机制[J]. *价格月刊*, 2015(12):70-75.
- [4] 刘玉敏, 靳琳琳. 基于改进服务质量模型的机场客运服务质量测评[J]. *经济经纬*, 2017, 34(06):81-86.
- [5] 王艺儒, 刘雪晶, 韩希等. 基于 WSR 方法论的机场货站物流服务质量评价体系构建研究[J]. *中国物流与采购*, 2022, No. 660(23):56-58.
- [6] 田雪, 王丹丹, 王晨. 航空地面物流服务质量评价模型研究——以首都国际机场为例[J]. *价格月刊*, 2018, No. 499(12):50-56.

